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Some Novel Adducts of Heterocyclic Amine N-Oxide with Tin(II) Halides and Isothiocyanate

B. K. DWIVEDI*

Department of Chemistry, B. S. N. V. Degree College,
Lucknow

and

T. N. SRIVASTAVA

Department of Chemistry, Lucknow University,
Lucknow-226 007

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A survey of literature¹⁻⁹ reveals that excepting some isolated studies, no systematic attempt has so far made to study the coordinative interaction of tin(II) derivatives with heterocyclic amine *N*-oxides. In the present communication nineteen new molecular adducts of general formula, $\text{SnX}_2 \cdot \text{L}$ [where $\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{NCS}$ and $\text{L} = 2-, 3-, 4\text{-picoline } N\text{-oxide}$ (2-, 3-, 4-PicO), lutidine *N*-oxide (LutO), quinoline *N*-oxide (QO), isoquinoline *N*-oxide (IsqO), and 2,2'-dipyridyl *NN'*-dioxide (DipyO₂)] and $\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2 \cdot 2\text{L}$ (where $\text{L} = \text{QO}$, and IsqO), have been synthesised and characterised.

Experimental

Anhydrous tin(II) chloride and bromide¹⁰, anhydrous tin(II) isothiocyanate¹¹, QO^{12} , IsqO^{13} and DipyO_2^{14} were prepared by the reported methods, and PicO and LutO (Aldrich) were used as such.

Infrared spectra (KBr) of the heterocyclic amine *N*-oxides and those of their adducts were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrophotometer (4000-400 cm^{-1}) and the far-ir spectra of a few representative compounds were recorded in CsI on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer (600-200 cm^{-1}). Molar conductance of complexes soluble in nitrobenzene were measured at $10^{-3} M$ concentration with the help of a Phillip's PR 9500 magic eye conductivity bridge using dip type conductivity cell at room temperature. Molecular weights in nitrobenzene solution were determined cryoscopically using Beckmann thermometer of $\pm 0.01^\circ$ accuracy. Thermogravimetric analyses were carried out on a Keroy K₈O T.G.A. apparatus at Lucknow University. Melting point of the compounds was obtained by means of a Toshniwal electrically operated melting point apparatus in open capillary and are uncorrected.

Microanalyses for carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were done at Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow. Tin and halogen were determined gravimetrically as tin(IV) oxide and silver halide, respectively.

Synthesis of heterocyclic amine N-oxide adducts: The complexes were prepared by the direct interaction of tin(II) chloride, bromide and isothiocyanate with heterocyclic amine *N*-oxides in absolute methanol.

The analytical data collected indicate that all the heterocyclic amine *N*-oxides form 1:1 (metal:ligand) adduct with tin(II) halides and isothiocyanate except quinoline *N*-oxide and isoquinoline *N*-oxide, which gave both 1:1 and 1:2 adducts. The 1:1 adducts of tin(II) isothiocyanate with QO or IsqO were prepared by adding a solution of tin(II) isothiocyanate (0.01 mmol) to a solution of QO or IsqO (0.01 mmol).

Results and Discussion

All compounds were obtained from very similar synthetic conditions. The interaction of 2-, 3-, 4-PicO, LutO, QO, IsqO with tin(II) bromide and isothiocyanate, yielded 1:1 solid complexes. Attempts to prepare 1:2 metal:ligand ratio compound by the method of Morrison and Haendler⁸ also yielded 1:1 complexes. Tin(II) isothiocyanate, however, yielded both 1:1 and 1:2 complexes with QO and IsqO ligands.

The complexes are well defined crystalline solid with sharp melting point and are not appreciably affected by atmospheric oxygen and moisture except $\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2 \cdot 2\text{PicO}$, which slowly decomposes on standing. Most of them are soluble in nitrobenzene, but sparingly soluble in other common organic solvents.

The molecular weight of the complexes soluble in nitrobenzene determined cryoscopically corresponds to monomeric formula weight. The molar conductance value of $10^{-3} M$ solution of the complexes which are sufficiently soluble in nitrobenzene at room temperature (20°) are in the range 3.26-4.26 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$, indicate their non-electrolytic character. These results are in good agreement with the previous report on tin(II) thiocyanate, which is monomeric in acetone solution and non-electrolyte in ethanol solution⁹.

Thermogravimetric analysis: The thermogravimetric analysis of some of the compounds were carried out and the loss of weight of the compounds was measured manually at various interval of time.

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From the pyrolysis curves of tin(II) isothiocyanate adducts with heterocyclic amine *N*-oxides two step weight loss is evident. In the first step the ligand molecule is lost leaving behind Sn(NCS)₂, which on further heating decomposes to SnO₂ and the nonvolatile residue corresponds well with the theoretical weight.

Infrared spectra : The ir absorption frequencies of diagnostic value are listed in the Table 1. The formation of molecular adducts is unequivocally indicated by the large shifts to lower frequency side of the N-O stretching bands in the spectra of the adducts compared to those of the pure ligand. A band of very strong intensity in the range 1180-1264 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the heterocyclic amine *N*-oxides has been assigned to this mode of vibration, which undergoes a significant negative shift of about 50-120 cm⁻¹ on complexation and is in good agreement with the earlier reports. The lowering of the N-O stretching frequency on complexation is attributed to coordination from the oxygen atom of the bases to the metal atom causing a decrease in π -character of the N-O bond. In the present investigation the shift in the N-O stretching frequency is ~120 cm⁻¹ in the 3-PicO adduct but an average of ~63 cm⁻¹ is observed in other complexes which is in good agreement with that reported for tin(II) chloride, methyl substituted pyridine *N*-oxide adducts⁷. It is not possible to draw conclusion about the relative donor strength of different heterocyclic amine *N*-oxide studied from

the ir data. But the extent of negative shift in ν_{N-O} may be considered to determine the relative donor strength of different heterocyclic amine *N*-oxide towards tin(II) halides and thiocyanate. As apparent from the data listed in the Table 1 the order is as follows: (i) Sn(NCS)₂ adducts: 3-PicO > 4-PicO > DipyO₂ > IsqO > 2-PicO > LutO > QO, (ii) SnBr₂ adducts: 3-PicO > LutO > 4-PicO > 2-PicO > DipyO₂ > QO = IsqO, (iii) SnCl₂ adducts: IsqO > DipyO > QO.

NCS Bonding : In the spectra of adducts of tin(II) isothiocyanate with heterocyclic amine *N*-oxide absorption due to ν_{C-N} , ν_{C-S} and δ_{NCS} have been identified at 2030 ± 30, 815 ± 15 and 480 ± 10 cm⁻¹, respectively, which agree well with *N*-bonded thiocyanate⁸. It is also interesting to note that as the size of the complexing ligand increases, the C-N stretching frequency decreases, and consequently the degree of bridging decreases.

Far-infrared spectra : Sn-O stretching vibration occurs over an exceptionally wide range of frequency depending upon the nature of bonding between the two atoms and also mass and basicity of the Lewis base. The Sn-O stretching absorption has been identified at 332 cm⁻¹ in tin(II) perchlorate trihydrate¹⁵, while in the dioxane complex it is either at 200-240 cm⁻¹ or is obscured by the ligand vibration at ~270 cm⁻¹. Zuckerman¹⁶ identified Sn-O stretching at 340 cm⁻¹ in tin(II) hydroxide and another strong band at 575 cm⁻¹, which suggested two modes of Sn-O attachment in solid tin(II)

TABLE 1—INFRARED FREQUENCIES OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	ν_{N-O} cm ⁻¹	$\Delta(N-O)$ cm ⁻¹	Thiocyanate frequencies (cm ⁻¹)		
			ν_{CN}	ν_{CS}	δ_{NCS}
2-PicO	1250	—			
SnBr ₂ .2-PicO	1180	70			
Sn(NCS) ₂ .2-PicO	1187	63	2000-1994 vs	880 vs	*
3-PicO	1275	—			
SnBr ₂ .3-PicO	1156	119			
Sn(NCS) ₂ .3-PicO	1155	120	2020-2100 vs	800 vs	470 s
4-PicO	1250	—			
SnBr ₂ .4-PicO	1175	75			
Sn(NCS) ₂ .4-PicO	1178	77	2060 2040 vs	825 vs	490 s
LutO	1246	—			
SnBr ₂ .LutO	1166	80			
Sn(NCS) ₂ .LutO	1186	60	2040-2020 vs	828 vs	515 s
QO	1230	—			
SnCl ₂ .QO	1180	50			
SnBr ₂ .QO	1175	55			
Sn(NCS) ₂ .QO	1176	54	2060 vs	820 vs	*
Sn(NCS) ₂ .2QO	1180	50	2040 vs	800 vs	480 s
IsqO	1180	—			
SnCl ₂ .IsqO	1120	60			
SnBr ₂ .IsqO	1125	55			
Sn(NCS) ₂ .IsqO	1100	80	2060 vs	810 vs	*
Sn(NCS) ₂ .2-IsqO	1120	60	2040 vs	826 s	490 s
DipyO ₂	1264	—			
	1260	—			
SnCl ₂ .DipyO ₂	1213	53			
	1198	71			
SnBr ₂ .DipyO ₂	1215	51			
	1195	69			
Sn(NCS) ₂ .DipyO ₂	1190	72	2000 vs	827 vs	

* Spectra recorded up to 650 cm⁻¹.

hydroxide. In the present investigation an absorption at 315-385 cm^{-1} in the spectra of adducts has been assigned to this mode of vibration, which unequivocally supports the oxygen atom being the donating centre in various heterocyclic amine *N*-oxide. Two Sn-O stretching mode of vibration at 345 and 315 cm^{-1} in the adduct $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot \text{DipyO}_2$ support bidentate character of the ligand.

The bands at ~ 255 and 265 cm^{-1} of weak intensity, observed in tin(II) isothiocyanate were assigned to Sn←N stretching vibration and is consistent with the presence at two crystallographically distinct N-bonded thiocyanate groups as shown recently by X-ray diffraction. The corresponding bands in the adducts are observed at ~ 270 and 260 cm^{-1} , which is lower than reported earlier by Nakamoto¹⁷ and Bhide¹⁸ in some tin(II) complexes containing Sn-N bond. A slight decrease in $\nu_{\text{Sn-N}}$ may be due to the lower oxidation state and higher coordination number of the tin metal.

The Sn-Cl stretching vibration has been identified at about 280 cm^{-1} , which is in agreement with earlier reports on tin(II) chloride adducts⁸. The Sn-Br stretching vibration could not be identified in the present investigation as it lies beyond the recorded range of the vibration.

Thus, on the basis of foregoing discussion and analogy with the previous work, the molecular adducts $\text{SnX}_2 \cdot \text{L}$ (where X=Br or NCS, and L=2-PicO, 3-PicO, 4-PicO, LutO, QO and IsqO), in which tin is three-coordinated, may have pyramidal structure due to sp^3 hybridization in which one of the sites is occupied by a stereochemically active lone pair. The adducts $\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_2 \cdot 2\text{L}$, [where L=QO or IsqO] and $\text{SnX}_2 \cdot \text{L}$ (where X=Cl, Br or NCS, and L=a bidentate ligand, DipyO_2), in which tin is four-coordinated may have trigonal bipyramidal structure, with stereochemically active lone pair occupying one of the sites.

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References

1. J. D. DONALDSON, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **8**, 287.
2. J. S. MORRISON and H. M. HAENDLER, *J. Nucl. Chem.*, 1967, **29**, 393.
3. J. K. LEEB and P. A. FLINN, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1968, **48**, 882.
4. V. I. GOLDANSKII, V. V. KHRAPOV, V. Y. ROZHEV, T. N. TUMAROKOVA and D. E. SURPINA, *Dokl. Akad. Nauk SSSR*, 1968, **183**, 864.
5. J. D. DONALDSON and D. G. NICHOLSON, *J. Chem. Soc. A*, 1970, 146.
6. E. HOUGH and D. G. NICHOLSON, *J. Chem. Soc. Dalton Trans.*, 1976, 1782.
7. J. W. KAUFFMAN, D. H. MOOR and B. J. WILLIAMS, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, **39**, 1165.
8. K. D. CHUGR, P. UMAPATHY and D. SEN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 864.
9. T. B. ABSI, R. S. MAKHIJA and M. ONYSZCHUK, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1978, **56**, 2039.
10. T. N. SRIVASTAVA and B. K. DWIVEDI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, **19**, 599.
11. B. R. CHAMBERLAIN and W. MOSER, *J. Chem. Soc. A*, 1969, 854.
12. E. OOHAI, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1953, **18**, 534.
13. M. ROBINSON and B. ROBINSON, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1956, **21**, 1337.
14. *J. Pharm. Soc. Jpn.*, 1955, **75**, 731.
15. C. G. DAVIES and J. D. DONALDSON, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1968, **30**, 2635.
16. W. D. HONRICK and J. J. ZUKERMAN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1976, **15**, 3034.
17. D. TEVAULT and K. NAKAMOTO, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1976, **15**, 1282.
18. S. N. BHIDE, P. UMAPATHY and D. N. SEN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 861.

Transition Metal Schiff Base Chelates as Ligands towards Tin(II) Halides and -Isothiocyanate

B. K. DWIVEDI*

Department of Chemistry, B. S. N. V. Degree College, Lucknow and

I. N. SRIVASTAVA

Department of Chemistry, Lucknow University, Lucknow-226 007

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THE transition metal-Schiff base chelates derived from tetradentate or bidentate Schiff bases have been extensively studied as ligands towards transition and non-transition metal ions and have been reviewed^{1,2}. Among the group IVB metals tin(IV) and tin(II) halides³ are reported to yield neutral 1:1 adducts with *N,N'*-ethylenebis(salicylideneimino)metal(II) M Salen, M=Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}, which have been shown to coordinate through phenolic O atoms. It has also been shown that Co^{II}(Salen)SnX₂ undergoes halide exchange in polar solvents, but exchange does not occur in the Co^{II}(Salen)SnX₂ adduct. However, studies using transition metal Schiff base complexes as ligands towards tin(II) acceptors are scarce.

In the present investigation several tin(II) isothiocyanate adducts of M Salen have been synthesised and characterised. Recently Srivastava *et al.*⁴ have also reported the synthesis and characterisation of binuclear adducts of organotin(IV) chlorides with the metal chelates of tetradentate Schiff bases derived from ketones such as acetylacetone, benzoylacetone and *o*-hydroxyacetophenone. It was considered of interest to study further the coordinative interaction of tin(II) halides and isothiocyanate with complex metal chelate ligands